

Open Science Droplets 02

Collaborative Science online, Github

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 email from Galileo

Hi again!

Thanks for sending me the notebook you prepared but I cannot open it. How can I see it? Also, I will be travelling during the following days, if you could send me something I can explore from my mobile phone, that would be great!

Cheers,

Galileo

Motivation

- ▶ In session 01 we created a Jupyter notebook
- ▶ Now we want to share it with our collaborator
- ▶ Include version control
- ▶ Use an online service (persistent backup and availability)
- ▶ First stage: basic functionality without git (no command line for now)

Requirements

- ▶ Account on github.com (or similar Gitlab, Bitcucket)
- ▶ Something to share

Plan

- ▶ Start an account
- ▶ Start a repository (Description, README, LICENSE)
- ▶ Upload files
- ▶ Make changes to file and commit them
- ▶ View differences and history
- ▶ Share your work!
- ▶ Collaborate: issues

New problem

- ▶ My colleague can see the notebook but cannot execute it
- ▶ Solutions in the next session!

Reference Material

- ▶ To learn more: Github Guides <https://guides.github.com/>
- ▶ Jake Vanderplas: <https://bit.ly/36z1lyG>
- ▶ Which license to use? <https://choosealicense.com/>

